

COMPOSITE SOLID ROCKET PROPELLANT MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

We have carried out a study of urethane crosslinked polyether composite propellants using spectroscopic and mechanical analysis. The objective of this work was to characterize the effect that variation in crosslink functional group distribution has on the mechanical properties of composite propellants. Gumstocks and composite propellant materials cured with commercial polyisocyanates such as N - 100 were compared to those cured with a trifunctional isocyanate, octyl triprimary isocyanate, OCTYPI. The results show a far greater distribution of functional groups with N-100 cured materials than in those cured with OCTYPI.

KEYWORDS: Polyurethane; Composite; Propellants; Cure; Crosslinking; Characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The most common class of solid rocket propulsion systems are the composite type, composed primarily of: organic polymers or binders like hydroxy-terminated polyethers and olefins; various types of fuels such as powdered aluminium metal, crystalline oxidizers like ammonium perchlorate, AP, or ammonium nitrate, AN; additives, such as plasticizers, catalysts, etc., and a curative or crosslinking agent.

The crosslinking agent is a polyisocyanate which reacts with difunctional hydroxy-terminated polymer during processing to give an elastomeric

polyurethane network. The elastomeric network often makes up only about ten percent of the total weight of the propellant but it is responsible for performing a variety of tasks. It not only "binds" the propellant together into its final form but it also must have the required viscoelastic properties to survive all the static and dynamic loads and stresses that are imposed during fabrication, transportation, storage and firing of the motor (1).

One commonly used curative is Mobay's Desmodur N-100. The curative N-100 is made by a catalyzed oligomerization of hexamethylene diisocyanate in the presence of a small amount of water. A variety of products and by-products are formed during this reaction, these compounds have a variety of different functional groups in the backbone and an isocyanate functionality that ranges from 2 to 10 with the average at 3.5. The N-100 is not purified and is used as is. Some of the problems that result are excessive crosslinking, unnecessary inter-chain and intra-chain hydrogen bonding interactions, and high batch-to-batch variability.

C. S. Youn-Kim demonstrated that the mechanical properties of polyurethane networks could be improved by substituting a purely trifunctional isocyanate, 1,3,5-pentane triisocyanate, for N-100. However, secondary hydroxy-terminated polymers gave no network formation when 1,3,5-pentane triisocyanate was used (2). Presumably this was due to incomplete reaction between the secondary isocyanate and the secondary hydroxy-terminated polymer. This indicated the need for all primary triisocyanate curatives.

Through a critical analysis of crosslinking agents used in polyurethane network formation we have attempted to qualitatively correlate curative structure with network mechanical properties (3). From this analysis we designed and targeted for synthesis an optimum curative structure, an all primary triisocyanate curative.

2. SYNTHESIS

We have synthesized, octyltriprimary isocyanate, OCTYPI, via a six step route (See Scheme 1.), the synthetic details of which were reported previously (4). This crosslinking agent was targeted because it embodies the key structural features we feel are important: all primary isocyanates, which gives a complete cure with the secondary-hydroxy groups of the polymer; trifunctionality, which provides a network when employing difunctional pre-polymers, both of these features minimize the number of non-load-bearing chains or loops in the cured material; a flexible all carbon backbone, which reduces the unnecessary inter-chain and intra-chain hydrogen bonding interactions present in the network when the commercial polyisocyanate Desmodur N-100 is used (See Figure 1.); at least a 1,5 disposition of the isocyanate groups, which allows synthesis of the

isocyanates in greater yield; and a low equivalent weight, which gives a lower weight of curative in the final formulation.

Scheme 1. OCTYPI synthesis.

FIGURE 1. Polymer crosslinked with N-100

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The reaction of an isocyanate with an alcohol under ideal conditions gives a urethane. Side reactions can occur to yield urea, biuret, uretidione, isocyanurate, and allophanate functional groups (See Figure 2.). When these side reactions occur during network formation the quality of the elastomer is severely degraded because they form elastically ineffective loops in the network. In similar polyether networks it has been shown that 5% side reactions reduce the modulus by 80% (5).

FIGURE 2. Possible network functional groups.

We were therefore interested in characterizing the functional group distribution in our elastomeric networks.

We have carried out a study of the cure of a secondary hydroxy-terminated polyether, glycidyl azide polymer (GAP), with OCTYPI (See Figure 3.) using ^{13}C NMR (CP/MAS) (6) and FTIR. The difunctional GAP used had a M_w of 2195 g/mol and a M_n of 1945 g/mol ($M_w / M_n = 1.13$) as determined by G.P.C. and was prepared by Rocketdyne. The cure ratio (NCO/OH) was 1.0:1.0. The reaction was first carried out without a catalyst. The initial temperature was 65°C for 28 hours and was then increased to 75°C for the remainder of the cure.

small portion of the crosslinking agent may still be present. Another possible factor is the post-cure realignment of interchain hydrogen bonds (7).

To be practically useful the cure time must be much shorter than 72 hours, therefore, we prepared GAP cured with OCTYPI (cure ratio 1.00:1.03) using a combination of two catalysts, triphenyl bismuth and dibutyl tin dilaurate (0.02% wt.).

To attempt to more completely characterize the network, we examined the network or gumstock by ^{13}C NMR (CP/MAS). We were interested in determining the type of crosslinks, ie., urethane, urea, allophanate, biuret, etc., and extent of side reactions and amount of hydrogen bonding present.

It is apparent from the spectra that ^{13}C / ^{15}N labelling will be necessary to quantitatively compare the type of crosslinks in N-100 cured GAP gumstock to those in gumstocks cured with OCTYPI. We attempted to obtain ^{15}N NMR (CP/MAS) spectra of the N-100/GAP and OCTYPI/GAP gumstock, however no signals were observed. This may be due to a number of factors. First we were only looking at natural abundance material, secondly these gumstocks have low crosslink density and therefore low concentration of N-15 spins. The absence of any signal from the azide group may be because there are no directly attached hydrogens to allow cross polarization to occur between the N-15 and proton spin systems.

Some information, however, may be extracted from the carbonyl region of the ^{13}C NMR (CP/MAS) spectra. Inspection of this region reveals that the resonance at 156 ppm from N-100 cured GAP gumstock has 3 times the width at half height than the resonance at 156 ppm from gumstock cured with OCTYPI. These resonances can be assigned to either urethane or biuret type of carbonyls in the networks. One possible explanation for this difference in peak widths is, that more carbonyls are involved in hydrogen bonding in the N-100 cured GAP gumstock than in the gumstock cured with OCTYPI. A calculation, based on the known structure of OCTYPI and the limited information available on the exact composition of N-100 (8), shows that there should be about twice as many N-H's in the N-100/GAP gumstock than in the OCTYPI/GAP gumstock.

To confirm this we obtained ^{13}C NMR (MAS, neat) and ^{15}N NMR (benzene and benzene/ether) of N-100 (a viscous oil). The ^{13}C NMR spectra show previously uncharacterized components of N-100, namely uretidione and isocyanurate structures (148,151 ppm). Further

conformation of these assignments comes from the ^{15}N NMR spectra where the uretedione and isocyanurate ^{15}N resonances are observed at -233.04 ppm. The remaining resonances can be assigned to biuret-type at -246.17 ppm, urea-type at -280.01ppm and isocyanate at -342.88 ppm(9). From integration of all the carbonly signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectra we see that the distribution of functional groups in N-100 is 44% Biuret/urea, 12% uretedione/ isocyanurate, and 46% isocyanate. This confirms our earlier claim, that there are about twice as many N-H's in the N-100/GAP gumstock than in the OCTYPI/GAP gumstock. This assumes similar cure chemistry for the two systems. It should be noted that the residual catalyst and by-products in N-100 will most likely increase the side reactions that degrade the mechanical properties of the propellant. Furthermore, removal of the deleterious hydrogen bonds in the gumstocks by employing OCTYPI as the crosslinking agent should also improve the overall mechanical properties of gumstocks and the fully formulated propellants.

Preliminary mechanical testing results (See Table 1.) using OCTYPI in a model composite propellant system (See Table 2.) lends some support to this prediction. When this propellant is compared to similar N-100/GAP propellant cured with the same catalysts the mechanical properties show it to be a much harder less elastomeric material (See Table 3).

TABLE 1 OCTYPI/GAP COMPOSITE PROPELLANT FORMULATION

GAP-8.85%,	MNA-0.50%,	TMETN-15.00%
GAP(A)-3.00%	CARBON-0.50%	Al powder-1.00%
HMX-5.00%	AN-65%	OCTYPI-0.65%

TABLE 2 MECHANICAL TESTING RESULTS

Initial Modulus (E_0)-242 psi
 Maximum strain (E_m)-20%
 Maximum Stress σ_m -38 psi

TABLE 3 N-100/GAP MECHANICAL TESTING RESULTS

Initial Modulus (E_0)-2463 psi
 Maximum strain (E_m)-3.9 %
 Maximum Stress σ_m -66 psi

4. CONCLUSION

OCTYPI a new triisocyanate crosslinking agent for secondary hydroxy-terminated difunctional polymers has been synthesized and has been shown to successfully cure glycidyl azide polymer, GAP. From our spectroscopic and mechanical studies we have confirmed that the use of a purely trifunctional crosslinking agent without the excess polar functional groups present in the backbone, as in N-100, can significantly reduce the amount of deleterious hydrogen bonding in these network (10). Furthermore, since OCTYPI is distillable, and is a single molecular structure, bath-to-batch variation during composite propellant processing should be improved.

5. REFERENCES

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